

RASA DHATU- RESPONSIBLE FOR OBESITY AND EMACIATION-AN ANALYTICAL REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda is an ancient science which describes various methods to make our daily life healthy. Dosha, Dhatu and Mala are the basic three pillars of life. Out of these Dhatu does the main function of holding the body elements together There are seven Dhatu in our ayurvedic classic such as Rasa, Rakta, Mansa, Meda, Asthi, Majja and Shukra. Rasa Dhatu is the first Dhatu and it plays an important role because rasa dhatu is formed first and it is responsible for forming all the next six Dhatu accordingly. Vitiating status of Rasadhātu can affect the all other Dhatu and finally may deteriorate the health of an individual. In this article we are going to discuss the role of Rasadhātu in Sthoulyata (Obesity) and karshyata. According to Acharya Sushruta If the Rasa is not formed accurately it leads to many systemic infections. Obesity and Emaciation both depends on the quality and quantity of Rasa Dhatu, its

distribution, conversion, and utilization.

KEYWORDS: Rasa Dhatu, Dhatu metabolism, Sthoulyata, Emaciation.

INTRODUCTION

According to Ayurveda the origin of body is from Ahara. After proper metabolic process the food ingredients changes into Anna-rasa or Adhyarasa Dhatu, which helps in the formation and nutrition of the other dhatus of the body. Rasadhātu is the first formed Dhatu from food metabolic process. Rasa dhatu helps in nourishment, development and maintenance of the body. Mostly problems arise when a person becomes Sthoulyata or Karshyata and it is due to the Rasa Dhatu. Sthoulyata itself is due to many other diseases or we can say these diseases are the

combination of many other diseases. The feature of the Rasa Dhatu is dependent upon the strength of Agni. Food and liquid ingredient are initially digested in the gastro intestinal tract and, turned into Ahara Rasa. This fluid then continue metabolism by the Rasagni to form Rasa Dhatu. The condition of Agni states the quality of Rasa produced. When the Rasagni is sluggish, the capability of transformation is reduced. When the Rasagni is simply too active, it smoothly converts Ahara Rasa to Rasa Dhatu.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

To understand the concept of Rasadhatu and its relation to obesity and emaciation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Literature search- Review of literature regarding Rasa Dhatu and Sthaulya are collected from Brihatrayi and available commentaries on it and research articles are also searched from various websites.

Type of study- Conceptual study

Rasa is the first Dhatu formed after complete digestion of food and due to its continuous circulation is called as Rasa. The function of Rasa Dhatu is Preenana (Nutrition). Two kinds of Rasa Dhatu present in the body, one is Sthayi Dhatu and another is Poshaka Dhatu. Heart is the main site of Rasa Dhatu When Rasa Dhatu is functioning properly helps within the formation of other Dhatus and additionally nourishes the body and also improves skin texture. If Rasa- dusti existing either due to Vriddhi (increase in quantity) or due to Kshaya (decrease in quantity) of Rasa Dhatu then various diseases has been occurred.

“Raso api shleshmwat” means Rasadhatu has Ashraya Ashrayi Sambandha with Kapha Dhatu. So vitiation in terms of Vruddhi or Kshaya also affects the same as of with the Rasadhatu.

Rasavaha Srotas - It is the passage of circulating Rasa all over the body. It originates from the heart and circulates Rasa by ten vessels. According to Acharya Sushruta the same organs and channels form pranavaha srotas. This means the heart and channels transporting Rasa also carry vital force (prana) in the body.

Clinical features of vitiation of rasavaha srotas

- Dislike towards food, anorexia, altered sense of taste, incapability to identify tastes, nausea, heaviness in the body, lethargy, bodyache, fever, blackouts, anemia, obstruction of channels, impotence, tiredness (Angavasada), emaciation, diminished Agni, and wrinkling of skin and greying of hair.

Role of Rasdhatu as vitiated factor in disease: Ras Dhatu is involved in the pathogenesis of many diseases like Jwara, metabolic disorder including diabetes (Prameha) and emaciation including tuberculosis (Shosha) The extremes of body frames i.e. obesity (Sthaulya) and emaciation (Karshya) depend on the quantity and quality of Rasa Dhatu, its distribution, conversion, and utilization in the body. These two conditions are risk factors for a wide range of metabolic disorders and lifestyle disorders.

Importance of Rasdhatu

Ayurveda mentioned that formation of Sthula, Krusha and Madhya Sharir depends on Dravyataha, Gunataha & Karmataha Vriddhi, Kshaya & Sthitee of Rasadhatu. Rasa is first Dhatu, which is responsible for nourishment of all body elements, & further Dhatus. Formation of Rasadhatu depends on type of food taken. More intake of Guru, Sheet, Mrudu Gunatmaka Aahara leads to Rasa-vriddhi which further outcomes in Sthoulya. It may be due to Prithvi & Aap Mahabhuta predominance in Guru, Sheet, Mrudu, Snigdha, Madhur, Sthira, Pichhil Gunatmaka Aahar. Rasadhatu has similar things as that of Kapha. Therefore, vitiation of Kapha causes vitiation in properties of Rasadhatu, which further leads to vitiation of Meda Dhatu because Rasa and meda are the ashrayiashaya of kapha dosha.

Etiology of sthaulya

रसनिमित्तमेव स्थौल्यं कार्श्यम्

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In Ayurveda there is no distinct definition of Sthaulya like other disease. An individual whose increased Meda Dhatu (Adipose tissue) makes his hips, Abdomen and breasts Pendulous and whose vitality is much less as compared to his body size is called as "Sthaulya". Obesity is major health problem in India. Obesity is chronic and increasingly common disease characterized by excess body fat. Obesity is normally caused by a sedentary lifestyle, lack of physical work and irregular diet and sleep pattern, stress. Obesity giving rise

to many serious health problems like coronary artery disease, type2 diabetes mellitus, respiratory diseases, hypertension, stroke, osteoarthritis, cancer (ovarian, breast, endometrial, gall bladder, prostate, colon), sleep apnoea, infertility, gout, venous circulatory disease, dermatological problems, psychological problems (poor selfesteem, depression). According to Ayurveda, obesity can be compared with, Sthoulya' Modem Science defines obesity as a body mass index greater than 27 for men and 25 for women. Body mass index can be calculated as body weight in Kilograms per square meter of the body size. In other word it is approximately Equivalent to 120 percent of the ideal body weight.

Causes of overweight / obesity: The causes of obesity are very clearly explained in Ayurveda. The following reasons which are mentioned in Ayurveda increase the deposition of fat.

Pathogenesis of sthaulya

Improperly formed Rasa Dhatu → Accumulation of unprocessed nutrients → Excess nourishment of Meda Dhatu → Sthoulya.

Rasa Dhatu and Emaciation (Karshya)

Ayurvedic Perspective

In Karshya or emaciation, there is Rasa Dhatu Kshaya (depletion), leading to poor nourishment of all subsequent tissues. Despite adequate intake, improper digestion (Agnimandya) or defective Rasavaha Srotas results in malabsorption and undernourishment.

Causes of rasa kshay and Emaciation (Karshya)

- Poor or irregular diet
- Excessive fasting or physical exertion
- Psychological stress or anxiety
- Chronic diseases causing Agnimandya.

Pathogenesis of karshya

Defective Ahara Rasa → Decreased Rasa Dhatu → Inadequate nourishment of all Dhatus → Karshya.

Relationship between Plasma, tissue fluid and lymph

Plasma, tissue fluid and lymph are very similar to each other, except for location. These are basically fluids (aapya) contain water and their primary function is (preenan) to transport

dissolved substances (nutrients). Plasma is the fluid present in blood. Water is the main component of plasma (92%), others are Proteins (7%), and dissolved organic molecules (1%) (amino acids, glucose, lipids, and nitrogenous wastes), ions (Na⁺, K⁺ etc), traced elements and vitamins, and dissolved oxygen (O₂) and carbon dioxide (CO₂). The plasma that leaks out from the blood into tissue spaces is referred to as the tissue fluid or interstitial fluid. The tissue fluid contains fewer amounts of protein molecule than plasma. The hydrostatic pressure at the arteriole end of blood capillaries pushes fluid out from the blood into the extracellular space of tissues. Nutrients such as glucose, amino acids and oxygen are pushed out from the blood into the tissue fluid. These nutrients are utilized by cells in the tissue. Most of the fluid is absorbed into the capillaries at their venule end. The little remaining fluid is collected by the lymphatic system and is called as lymph.

DISCUSSION

Parameter	In Obesity (Sthoulya)	In Emaciation (Karshya)
Rasa Dhatu Status	Excessive but impure (Mala Rasa)	Deficient and unstable (Kshaya Rasa)
Agni (Metabolic Fire)	Manda Agni (low metabolism)	Vishama Agni (irregular metabolism)
Srotas	Blocked and sluggish	Depleted and weak
Upadhatus	Excess Stanya or menstrual irregularities	Depleted Stanya and Raja
Clinical Outcome	Over-nourishment → Fat accumulation	Under-nourishment → Wasting

Thus, both obesity and emaciation are outcomes of disturbed Rasa Dhatu metabolism—either excessive accumulation or inadequate formation. Maintenance of optimal Rasagni and Srotas patency is crucial for balance.

CONCLUSION

Rasa Dhatu serves as the critical determinant of body nourishment and metabolic stability. Its imbalance manifests as either obesity or emaciation depending on whether it is excessive or deficient. Maintaining the integrity of Agni and Rasavaha Srotas ensures proper Rasa Dhatu function and overall health. Integrative management combining Ayurvedic principles with nutritional science may provide effective solutions for modern metabolic disorders.

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